

Thyroid hormone receptor β (THRB) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : THRB encodes a nuclear hormone receptor for triiodothyronine (T_3) and is one of the several receptors for thyroid hormone, and known to mediate the biological activities of thyroid hormone. It has been implicated in deafness, human cone disorders or colour vision problems, breast cancer, resistance to thyroid hormone, clear cell renal cell cancer, esophageal squamous cell carcinoma, autism spectrum disorder, recovery after brain injury, aging, myotonic dystrophy type 1, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), familial dysalbuminemic hyperthyroxinemia (FDH), hypercholesterolemia, adenoid cystic carcinoma, osteoporosis and endometrial cancer, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of THRB, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors

*ML dicoveries of THRB synergy in Meningiomas

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in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: THRB, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Thyroid hormone receptor β (THR β)

The genome of avian erythroblastosis virus contains two independently expressed genetic loci (v-erb-A/B) whose activities are probably responsible for oncogenesis by the virus. Both loci are closely related to nucleotide sequences found in the DNA and RNA of chickens and other vertebrates. Vennström and Bishop [13] isolated and characterized chicken DNA homologous to v-erb-A/B. They found that the two viral genes were represented by separate domains within chicken DNA (c-erb-A/B), which were separated by a minimum of 12 kilobases (kb) of DNA and might not be linked at all. Their

findings indicated that the c-erb loci were normal vertebrate genes rather than genes of cryptic endogenous retroviruses, and that they might have a role in the metabolism of normal cells.

Jansson et al. [14] isolated the human DNA sequences complementary to the oncogenes v-erb-A/B of avian erythroblastosis virus from a genomic DNA library. Two clones, λ he-A-1/2 and λ he-A2, were related to the erbA gene and one to the erbB gene (λ he-B).

Weinberger et al. [15] found that the cDNA sequence of human c-erb-A (cellular counterpart of the viral oncogene v-erb-A), pointed that the protein encoded by the gene is related to the steroid hormone receptors. Their binding studies with the protein showed it to be a receptor for thyroid hormones.

Thompson et al. [16] isolated a complementary DNA clone derived from rat brain messenger RNA on the basis of homology to the human thyroid hormone receptor gene. Expression of this complementary DNA produced a high-affinity binding protein for thyroid hormones, while sequence analysis and the mapping the gene to a distinct human genetic locus pointed to the existence of multiple human thyroid hormone receptors. It was observed that mRNA from this gene was expressed in a tissue-specific fashion with highest levels in the central nervous system.

Studies on the analyses of steroid receptors have led to the identification of a superfamily of regulatory proteins that include receptors for thyroid hormone and the vertebrate morphogen retinoic acid. Evans [17] reviewed the mechanisms underlying morphogenesis and homeostasis via these receptor-related molecules in a wide range of species.

Thyroid hormone receptors (TR) are ligand-dependent, DNA-binding, trans-acting transcriptional factors belonging to the erb-A-related steroid/thyroid hormone receptor superfamily. Akihiro et al. [18] isolated the gene encoding human TR β 1 (hTR β 1), to better understand the structural and functional characteristics of TRs. They found that the coding region of hTR β 1 was highly conserved when compared with the chicken c-erbA gene which encoded an α -type chicken TR.

1.3. Roles of THRB in different disease

Congenital thyroid disorders are associated with **deafness**, indicating a requirement for thyroid hormone (T_3) and its receptors in the development of hearing. Two T_3 receptor genes, Tr- α/β are differentially expressed, although in overlapping patterns, during development. Forrest et al. [19] showed that Tr- β -deficient (THRB^{-/-}) mice exhibited a permanent deficit in auditory function across a wide range of frequencies. They observed that the auditory-evoked brainstem response (ABR) in THRB^{-/-} mice, although greatly diminished, displayed normal waveforms, thus suggesting that the primary defect resided in the cochlea. Their findings suggested that Tr- β controlled the maturation of auditory function but not morphogenesis of the cochlea.

Color vision is facilitated by distinct populations of cone photoreceptors in the retina. In rodents, cones expressing different opsin photopigments are sensitive to middle (M, 'green') and short (S, 'blue') wavelengths, and are differentially distributed across the retina. It is known that thyroid hormone receptor beta 2 (TR- β -2) is a ligand-activated transcription factor that is expressed in the outer nuclear layer of the

embryonic retina. Ng et al. [20] deleted THRB (encoding Tr- β -2) in mice, causing the selective loss of M-cones and a concomitant increase in S-opsin immunoreactive cones. The gradient of cone distribution was found to be disturbed, with S-cones becoming widespread across the retina. Their results indicated that cone photoreceptors throughout the retina had the potential to follow a default S-cone pathway and reveal an essential role for Tr- β -2 in the commitment to an M-cone identity. Thus, their findings showed the possibility that THRB mutations might be associated with **human cone disorders**.

Thyroid hormone (triiodothyronine, T₃) is a pleiotropic regulator of growth, differentiation and tissue homeostasis. Several TR- α/β receptor isoforms are expressed and contradictory literature exists on the relationship between circulating thyroid hormone levels, thyroid diseases and human cancer. In 1986, a connection between TR and cancer became evident when the chicken TR- α -1 was characterized as the c-erb-A proto-oncogene, the cellular counterpart of the retroviral v-erb-A oncogene. It is known that v-erb-A causes erythroleukemias and sarcomas in birds, and hepatocellular carcinomas in transgenic mice. In a review, González-Sancho et al. [21] show that together with other in vitro data indicating connections between TR and p53, Rb, cyclin D and other cell cycle regulators and oncogenes, results suggest that THRA and THRB might be involved in **human cancer**.

The thyroid hormone receptors (TR) have three major isoforms, TR α -1/2, and TR β -1; of which, THRB (gene encoding TR β -1), is considered a potential cancer suppressor. Ling et al. [22] investigated the aberrant silencing of THRB in **breast cancer** tissue and plasma by promoter hypermethylation and RT-PCR was used to examine THRB mRNA expression in the breast cancer tissues. It was observed that the expression of THRB mRNA in breast cancer tissues was lower than that in the normal tissues and hypermethylation was found in 32 of 40 breast cancer tissues and in 28 of 40 plasma samples. Their results indicated that hypermethylation (a gene silencing mechanism) of THRB was highly prevalent in breast cancer.

Resistance to thyroid hormone (RTH), a dominantly inherited disorder usually associated with mutations in THRB, is marked by higher levels of circulating thyroid hormones (including thyroxine), failure of feedback suppression of thyrotropin, and variable tissue refractoriness to thyroid hormone action. Raised energy expenditure and hyperphagia are recognized features of hyperthyroidism. Mitchell et al. [23] demonstrated that resting energy expenditure (REE) was substantially increased in adults and children with THRB mutations. Energy intake in RTH subjects was observed to increase, with marked hyperphagia particularly evident in children. Mitochondrial coupling index between ATP synthesis and mitochondrial rates of oxidation (estimated by ATP synthesis-to-TCA cycle flux, ratio) was found to be significantly decreased in RTH patients. Their data demonstrated that basal mitochondrial substrate oxidation is increased and energy production in the form of ATP synthesis is decreased in the muscle of RTH patients and that resting oxidative phosphorylation is uncoupled in this disorder. Their observations suggested that mitochondrial uncoupling in skeletal muscle is a major contributor to increased REE in patients with RTH, due to tissue selective retention of THRA sensitivity to elevated thyroid hormone levels.

TR- β -1 is a hormone-dependent transcription factor activated by 3,5,3'-triiodothyronine (T₃). Master et al. [24] hypothesized that reduced TR- β -1 expression in **clear cell**

renal cell cancer (ccRCC) resulted from regulatory effects of TR- β -1 5' and 3' untranslated regions (UTRs) on protein translation. They found reduced levels of TR- β -1 mRNA and protein levels in ccRCC and accompanied by absent D1 protein, a reduction in tissue T₃ concentration and 2-fold increase in miRNA-204. Their structural analysis of TR- β -1 UTR variants indicated that reduced TR- β -1 expression might be maintained in ccRCC by posttranscriptional mechanisms involving 5'UTRs and miRNA-204. The tumor suppressor activity of TR- β -1 pointed that reduced TR- β -1 expression and tissue hypothyroidism in ccRCC tumors was likely to be involved in the process of carcinogenesis or in maintaining a proliferative advantage to malignant cells.

Chemotherapy-related toxicities are difficult to predict before treatment and Miki et al. [25] investigated whether THRB genetic polymorphisms could serve as a potential biomarker in patients with **esophageal squamous cell carcinoma** (ESCC). For this, they analysed 49 Japanese patients with ESCC who received a definitive chemoradiotherapy (CRT) with 5-fluorouracil and cisplatin in conjunction with concurrent irradiation. They observed that the distribution of the 4 intronic SNPs, showed a significant difference between patients with/without severe acute leukopenia.

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neuro developmental disorder and thyroid hormone T₃ plays a role in early embryonic and central nervous system development as it mediates its function by binding to thyroid hormone receptors, TR- α/β . Alterations in T₃ levels and thyroid receptor mutations have been earlier implicated in neuropsychiatric disorders and have been linked to environmental toxins. Kalikiri et al. [26] performed genetic analysis of ligand binding domain of THRA and THRB receptor genes in 30 ASD subjects and in age matched controls from India, to explore the genetic variations in the components of the thyroid hormone pathway in ASD children. In a first, their study reports novel SNPs in the THRA and THRB receptor genes of ASD individuals.

Liu and Brent [27] reviewed the effect of thyroid hormone (TH) in normal brain development and promotion of recovery and neuronal regeneration after **brain injury** as it acts predominantly through the nuclear receptors, THRA and THRB. They state that in animal models, TH has been shown to be protective for the damage incurred from brain injury and may have a role to limit injury and promote recovery. Although clinical trials have not yet been reported, findings from in vitro and in vivo models have shown potential treatment strategies utilizing TH for protection and promotion of recovery after brain injury.

In a previous study, Aguayo-Mazzucato et al. [28] showed that TH triiodothyronine (T₃) enhanced β -cell functional maturation through induction of MAFA. Studies have shown that the high levels of T₃ have been linked to decreased life span in mammals and low levels to lengthened life span, which suggest a relationship between TH and **aging**. Aguayo-Mazzucato et al. [28] showed that T₃ increased p16^{Ink4a} (a β -cell senescence marker and effector) mRNA in rodent and human β -cells. They observed that both genes MAFA and p16^{Ink4a} were targets of TH via TH receptors (THRs) binding to specific response elements. Their results showed that T₃ could simultaneously induce both maturation (MAFA) and aging (p16^{Ink4a}) effectors and that these dichotomous effects are mediated through different THR isoforms.

Takeda et al. [29] observed the co-occurrence of RTH- β and **myotonic dystrophy type I** (DM1) in a Japanese family. They identified two mutations, P453A and C36Y, in

THRB, with exhibition of RTH- β in family members with THRB^{P453A}, two members with THRB^{C36Y} but without THRB^{P453A} had normal thyroid function. Further, they observed a triplet expansion in the dystrophin myotonia protein kinase gene, a hallmark of DM1, with 2 members, one with RTH- β and the other without. They found that the member with both RTHB and DM1 developed atrial fibrillation at the age of 16 years, which pointed to a synergistic impact on the heart.

The cognitive phenotype of RTHB has been reported to be similar to **attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)**. Uter et al. [30] used electrophysiological biomarkers of performance monitoring in RTHB to contribute further evidence on its phenotypical similarity to ADHD. Their findings revealed alterations in error detection and performance monitoring of RTHB patients, thus pointing to reduced error awareness. They observed that the electrophysiological phenotype of RTHB subjects with regard to action monitoring was indistinguishable from ADHD.

The alteration of TH-binding proteins, such as in **Familial Dysalbuminemic Hyperthyroxinemia (FDH)**, can mimic the abnormal serum thyroid tests typical of RTH. Dieu et al. [31] aimed to characterize a population referred to our center with suspected RTH and estimate the proportion of patients with FDH. They found 56 THRB variants (i.e., 38% of the 303 index cases, called RTHB group).

Pajek et al. [32] presented 3 siblings with THRB mutation (heterozygous disease-variant c.727C>T, p.Arg243Trp); of which two of them also had **hypercholesterolemia**, while all three had several other clinical characteristics of RTHB. The subjects were the first description of the known Slovenian cases with RTHB due to the mutation in the THRB gene. They hypothesized that hypercholesterolemia might be etiologically related with RTHB, as the severity of hormonal resistance varies among different tissues and hypercholesterolemia in patients with THRB variants might indicate the relatively hypothyroid state of the liver.

Schnoell et al. [33] analyzed protein levels of 44 patients with **adenoid cystic carcinoma** of the head and neck and found sodium iodide symporter (NIS) +ive in 72%, μ -crystallin (CRYM) +ive in 55%, and THRB +ive in 39% of the patients.

Osteoporosis is a metabolic syndrome, and the consumption of fructose has been linked to various metabolic diseases. Chen and Jiang [34] showed that fructose intake could exacerbate bone loss in murine models by facilitating the accumulation of cholesterol within the bones. For this, they identified THRB and protein kinase C ζ (PRKC ζ) as potential therapeutic targets for the treatment of osteoporosis. When they subjected mice to a high-fructose diet, they observed a reduction in bone density and a decrease in the osteogenic differentiation of bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMSCs) compared to those on a standard diet. Further, fructose treatment was found to decrease THRB expression while increasing PRKC ζ expression, that led to cholesterol accumulation and hindering the osteogenic differentiation of BMSCs. Thus, their study explained the molecular mechanisms by which fructose influenced osteogenesis through the THRB/PRKC ζ /cholesterol accumulation pathway in the context of osteoporosis.

Progestin resistance has emerged as a significant barrier to the conservative management of **endometrial cancer (EC)** and earlier studies have suggested that THRB is associated with progestin resistance in EC cells. For this, Yang et al. [35] constructed THRB-knockout RL95-2 (THRB^{-/-}/RL95-2) cells to investigate progestin resistance

mechanisms. They observed that canagliflozin (CANA) demonstrated a strong binding affinity for TR- β . Further, they found that both medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA) and CANA suppressed proliferation in RL95-2 cells, but MPA was ineffective in THRB^{-/-}/RL95-2 cells, thus pointing that THRB deficiency induced progestin resistance. Further, CANA was found to inhibit proliferation and promoted apoptosis in THRB^{-/-}/RL95-2 cells. Thus, THRB knockout activated retinoic acid pathway, leading to progestin resistance.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [36] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [37] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option

has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [37].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [38]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [39], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [36] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [36]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [40], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data

may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. THRB related synergies

Note - THRB was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of THRB were recorded.

3.1.1. THRB - individual genes

The following genes in combination with THRB showed high rankings - heat shock protein family B (small) member 6 (HSPB6), prominin 1 (PROM1), insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), elastin (ELN), neuron navigator 3 (NAV3), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), fibulin 1 (FBLN1), matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP2), seizure related 6 homolog like (SEZ6L), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), transmembrane protein 59 like (TMEM59L), secreted frizzled related protein 4 (SFRP4), AE binding protein 1 (AEBP1), EBF transcription factor 3 (EBF3), bone marrow stromal cell antigen 1 (BST1), GLI family zinc finger 1 (GLI1), cut like homeobox 2 (CUX2), ST8 alpha-N-acetylneuraminidase alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), podocalyxin like 2 (PODXL2), solute carrier family 30 member 3 (SLC30A3), hippocalcin like 4 (HPCAL4), connective tissue growth factor (CTGF / CCN2), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein 2 (LTBP2), proteolipid protein 1 (PLP1), matrilin 4 (MATN4), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), MBL associated serine protease 1 (MASP1), cingulin like 1 (CGNL1), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), matrilin 3 (MATN3), serpin family F member 1 (SERPINF1), peripherin (PRPH), sodium

voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), dual oxidase 1 (DUOX1), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), dual oxidase maturation factor 1 (DUOXA1), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), NKD inhibitor of WNT signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), reticulocalbin 3 (RCN3), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), secreted frizzled related protein 2 (SFRP2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2 (NTRK2), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), matrix metalloproteinase 16 (MMP16), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), meiosis 1 associated protein (M1AP), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of THRB with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS THRB									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T THRB									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
HSPB6 - THRB	157	388	273	334	PROM1 - THRB	77	341	376	377
IGF1 - THRB	106	289	267	296	ELN - THRB	223	239	315	265
NAV3 - THRB	48	228	241	311	SLC12A1 - THRB	7	301	377	389
FBLN1 - THRB	168	371	234	388	MMP2 - THRB	237	242	288	180
SEZ6L - THRB	218	211	316	328	SRPX - THRB	113	326	368	381
PCSK1N - THRB	61	244	313	248	SLC17A7 - THRB	75	302	262	277
TMEM59L - THRB	54	346	339	360	SFRP4 - THRB	56	308	369	298
AEBP1 - THRB	232	203	326	331	EBF3 - THRB	83	245	300	217
BST1 - THRB	269	283	254	261	GLI1 - THRB	58	287	210	213
CUX2 - THRB	250	311	371	299	ST8SIA1 - THRB	32	375	200	384
NPR3 - THRB	79	285	343	357	PODXL2 - THRB	17	295	370	379
SLC30A3 - THRB	15	306	357	383	HPCAL4 - THRB	256	297	327	312
CTGF - THRB	81	216	271	324	TRIM67 - THRB	175	366	353	303
LTBP2 - THRB	118	312	302	257	PLP1 - THRB	71	358	331	340
MATN4 - THRB	34	349	244	229	LAMP5 - THRB	97	392	390	391
MASP1 - THRB	64	231	351	321	CGNL1 - THRB	206	221	299	118
KIF1A - THRB	21	320	292	358	PODNL1 - THRB	2	235	308	385
MATN3 - THRB	41	262	317	329	SERPINF1 - THRB	138	369	225	208
PRPH - THRB	114	391	310	291	SCN7A - THRB	67	361	358	368
TTC29 - THRB	194	353	314	346	THBS1 - THRB	101	368	335	390
PLCB2 - THRB	278	108	229	275	DUOX1 - THRB	205	348	231	354
LHCGR - THRB	47	389	352	363	RBP4 - THRB	30	357	303	373
DUOXA1 - THRB	265	257	342	374	FGF7 - THRB	62	343	392	380
NKD1 - THRB	110	377	348	378	RCN3 - THRB	39	322	263	216
NXPH2 - THRB	127	387	269	392	SFRP2 - THRB	165	248	359	315
CHRN3 - THRB	3	384	391	382	NTRK2 - THRB	158	305	378	226
DRD2 - THRB	9	381	363	356	KCNA6 - THRB	31	290	385	372
MMP16 - THRB	214	229	224	58	SUSD3 - THRB	13	350	337	239

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between THRB VS Individual members.

influences - • Individual members w.r.t THRB with THRB – > HSPB6 / PROM1 / IGF1 / ELN / NAV3 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / MMP2 / SEZ6L / SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / TMEM59L / SFRP4 / AEBP1 / EBF3 / BST1 / GLI1 / CUX2 / ST8SIA1 / NPR3 / PODXL2 / SLC30A3 / HPCAL4 / CTGF / TRIM67 / LTBP2 / PLP1 / MATN4 / LAMP5 / MASP1 / CGNL1 / KIF1A / PODNL1 / MATN3 / SERPINF1 / PRPH / SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / PLCB2 / DUOX1 / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOXA1 / FGF7 / NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 / SFRP2 / CHRN3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / MMP16 / SUSD3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / HPGD / TMEM200A / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / HTRA1 / TVP23A / LDHD / CYP2S1 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ENHO / CPT1C / CCDC126 / STK32A / GPR183 / ITGAM / MAP6 / MACROD2 / STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / YPEL2 / PDE4DIP / CIITA / PLAG1 / EXT1 / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / CSF1 / PRKG1 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / KBTBD12 / PLAC9 / DACT3 / C2orf27A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / HACD2 / ITGB2-AS1 / ZNF883.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS THRB									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T THRB									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MYO1E - THRB	100	265	334	337	SLAMF8 - THRB	132	295	372	300
RUNX1 - THRB	193	372	375	278	MIAP - THRB	225	272	380	320
CHCHD6 - THRB	84	347	356	215	SIGLEC11 - THRB	63	271	360	264
SIGLEC16 - THRB	160	342	28	255	LRP5 - THRB	281	330	321	171
MXRA8 - THRB	115	363	215	260	NLRP3 - THRB	139	321	354	333
HPGD - THRB	282	224	243	18	TMEM200A - THRB	121	337	341	251
COL1A2 - THRB	98	327	384	256	TMEM71 - THRB	86	317	338	218
HTRA1 - THRB	240	309	344	146	TVP23A - THRB	359	266	204	240
LDHD - THRB	210	345	365	185	CYP2S1 - THRB	292	334	226	230
FILIP1L - THRB	104	382	307	352	RAB31 - THRB	66	386	323	267
NPNT - THRB	20	370	336	310	ENHO - THRB	231	37	203	242
CPT1C - THRB	295	205	117	212	CCDC126 - THRB	18	281	350	316
STK32A - THRB	239	85	250	243	GPR183 - THRB	89	354	386	326
ITGAM - THRB	148	234	305	204	MAP6 - THRB	316	230	230	40
MACROD2 - THRB	12	336	332	200	STARD5 - THRB	299	223	208	90
IL17D - THRB	262	314	227	112	PEAK1 - THRB	25	288	272	236
HEG1 - THRB	338	300	383	313	YPEL2 - THRB	35	356	382	273
PDE4DIP - THRB	336	277	320	266	CIITA - THRB	11	352	258	305
PLAG1 - THRB	137	390	374	348	EXT1 - THRB	308	299	379	281
EPHB3 - THRB	209	220	245	109	PYCR1 - THRB	154	335	256	297
CSF1 - THRB	130	367	388	272	PRKG1 - THRB	245	291	265	163
CYP4Z1 - THRB	152	344	355	279	CYP4X1 - THRB	5	378	367	314
RTN4RL2 - THRB	93	333	381	292	KBTBD12 - THRB	224	307	252	142
PLAC9 - THRB	291	19	239	201	DACT3 - THRB	352	249	318	198
C2orf27A - THRB	150	376	219	338	MT1F - THRB	271	284	240	139
ITGBL1 - THRB	178	332	328	221	DUSP27 - THRB	76	374	293	258
RNU6-529P - THRB	109	316	255	288	HACD2 - THRB	49	364	389	224
ITGB2-AS1 - THRB	304	246	294	102	ZNF883 - THRB	151	360	289	317

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between THRB VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic THRB 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of THRB-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t THRB	
HSPB6 / PROM1 / IGF1 / ELN / NAV3 ...	
SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / MMP2 / SEZ6L / SRPX ...	
PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / TMEM59L / SFRP4 ...	
AEBP1 / EBF3 / BST1 / GLI1 / CUX2 ...	
ST8SIA1 / NPR3 / PODXL2 / SLC30A3 ...	
HPCAL4 / CTGF / TRIM67 / LTBP2 / PLP1 ...	
MATN4 / LAMP5 / MASP1 / CGNL1 / KIF1A ...	
PODNL1 / MATN3 / SERPINF1 / PRPH ...	
SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / PLCB2 ...	
DUOX1 / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOXA1 / FGF7 ...	
NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 / SFRP2 / CHRNB3 ...	
NTRK2 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / MMP16 / SUSD3 ...	
MYO1E / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / CHCHD6 ...	
SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / MXRA8 ...	
NLRP3 / HPGD / TMEM200A / COL1A2 / TMEM71 ...	
HTRA1 / TVP23A / LDHD / CYP2S1 / FILIP1L ...	
RAB31 / NPNT / ENHO / CPT1C / CCDC126 ...	
STK32A / GPR183 / ITGAM / MAP6 / MACROD2 ...	
STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / YPEL2 ...	
PDE4DIP / CIITA / PLAG1 / EXT1 / EPHB3 ...	
PYCR1 / CSF1 / PRKG1 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 ...	
RTN4RL2 / KBTBD12 / PLAC9 / DACT3 ...	
C2orf27A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DUSP27 ...	
RNU6-529P / HACD2 / ITGB2-AS1 / ZNF883	THRB

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between THRB and Individual members.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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